

Standardising Drone Metadata for Enhanced Data Management in Precision Agriculture

Dr Kawsar P. Salam, Dr Dean Diepeveen, Dr Bob French, Jennifer Garlinge, Department of Primary Industries and Regional Development (DPIRD), Perth, Western Australia, Australia

Corresponding author: Dr Kawsar P. Salam, Data Modelling Specialist, email: Kawsar.salam@dpiird.wa.gov.au, Orcid ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9512-9939>

DPIRD's data management team has introduced the DPIRD Drone Metadata Framework (DDMF) to standardise the collection and recording of research metadata from drones equipped with high-resolution RGB, LiDAR, and hyperspectral cameras. This framework ensures compliance with FAIR data principles, aligns with DPIRD's data policies, and meets the requirements of external organisations such as the Grains Research and Development Corporation (GRDC) and the Australian Plant Phenomics Network (APPN).

This marks DPIRD's first widespread use of drones for precision agriculture. In the era of artificial intelligence, our scientists will generate vast amounts of field data collected by drones and other uncrewed aerial vehicles (UAVs). This data will be critical for machine learning and modelling algorithms, with drone imagery and associated metadata—such as camera sensor details, flight operations, and weather conditions—playing a key role.

Because drone-based data collection differs significantly from traditional field data collection, the DDMF provides an essential, efficient, and structured approach to managing this new data source effectively.

The following stakeholders will benefit from this drone metadata framework:

- Researchers
- External Parties
- Funding Organisations
- DPIRD
- Newly recruited research staff
- State
- National
- Community

The drone metadata framework (DDMF) has eight sections, each covering different types of drone data entities. Our team (the above authors) had several meetings, and after reviewing the literature on drone data collection, we listed seventy-two items.

1. Project Information

- Unique ID for APPN
- Project Title

- Project Contract Code
- Trial ID
- Location Name

2. Drone & Equipment Specifications

- Drone Model
- Drone Make
- Drone Weight
- Drone Type Rating
- Sensor Location on Drone
- Sensor gimbal or fix
- Risk Management Plan - Drones fly
- Drone operator accreditation
- Drone Registration
- Drone safety rules

3. Flight Operations & Environmental Conditions

- Operational records
- Flight Mission
- Flight Date
- Start Time Flight
- End Time Flight
- Total Number of Flights
- Flight Pattern Type (grid, vertical profile, forward lap)
- Drone Flight Distance from Ground Altitude (<120m etc)
- Flight time Temperature
- Flight time Humidity
- Flight time Wind Speed
- Flight time Cloud Cover
- Image Overlap Percentage (e.g., percentage of how much area of an image is stitched to the next image)
- Drone Flight Speed
- Flight ID (AVCRM no)

4. Pilot Details

- Pilot Name
- Pilot Mobile No

5. Imaging & Sensor Data Collection

- RGB Camera Model, Resolution & Frequency
- Multispectral Camera Model
- Multispectral Camera Spectral Bands (e.g., 4 or 8 or more bands)

- Multispectral Camera Spectral Resolution (e.g., 4K: 3840 x 2160 p or)
- Multispectral Camera frame rate per second (fps)
- Hyperspectral Camera Model
- Hyperspectral Camera Spectral Bands
- Hyperspectral Camera Spectral Resolution
- Hyperspectral Camera frame rate per second (fps)
- Model Thermal Camera (e.g., FLIR Vue Pro)
- Thermal Camera Resolution
- Thermal Camera frame rate per second (fps)
- LiDAR Camera (e.g., Velodyne Lidar Puck (VLP-16))
- LiDAR Camera Spectral Resolution
- LiDAR Camera frame rate per second (fps)

6. Data Processing & Storage

- Name of Raw Data Compression Method (e.g., Lossless compression method)
- Software used to create high-resolution stitched images (e.g., DroneDeploy, Pix4D, Agisoft Metashape, QGIS, WebODM, etc.)
- Automated geotagging images with GPS coordinates or manual georeferencing (yes-or-no)
- Type of Processed Image Output (Orthomosaic Imagery/tabular/gridded, etc.)
- Total Number of Images
- Unprocessed Image File Format (GeoTIFF, JPEG, PNG, LAS)
- Unprocessed (compressed) Image Storage URL (Objective) yes/no
- Unprocessed Image Data Size
- Processed Data Storage URL (Objective)

7. Target & Field Condition Information

- Target (e.g., crop, biomass, pasture, research trials, etc.)
- Target information field 1
- Target information field 2
- Target information field 3
- Target information field 4
- Field condition (at the time drone flying dry, wet, irrigated)

8. Compliance, Licensing & Metadata

- Licence applies to the dataset (CC-BY, CC-BY-ND, CC-BY-NC-SA, CC0, CC-BY-SA, CC-BY-NC, CC-BY-NC-ND, Other)
- Access rights for the dataset (e.g., Open, Restricted, Conditional, Embargoed)
- Privacy Compliance Followed (how & what?)
- Data Licensing Information
- Metadata Standard Template Version No
- Related Data ID Version Number
- Related Data ID Version Number - when and why

Sources

To keep the data recording job simple, time efficient and doable for researchers, we recommend all these 72 data entities be collected from the following sources:

- Aviation Compliance and Risk Management Software (AVCRM)
- Civil Aviation Safety Authority (CASA)
- Equipment Register (DPIRD)
- Researchers/Dynamics

Here is a diagram of the proportion of data sources:

All data items on the DDMF will have source links, and data will be automatically filled from the source links. Researchers would fill only 36% of data into Dynamics.

Flowchart:

The flow starts at Drone Metadata Data Items, goes into a Classification step, and then splits into four possible branches. The three branches pointing to external sources (AVCRM, CASA, Equipment Register) each proceed to an Auto-fill if available step (where the system populates the data automatically if possible). The User Input branch goes directly to User Fills Data, indicating manual entry. Finally, both the auto-filled data and the user-filled data lead to the Complete Form, signifying that the metadata item has been successfully recorded. This streamlined process ensures that whenever possible, data is pulled from existing data sources, reducing manual effort and only requiring user input when no auto-fill data is available.

References:

Alice Fremand, 2023, UAV Data Management Handbook, UK Polar Data Centre, British Antarctic Survey, https://nora.nerc.ac.uk/id/eprint/536392/1/UAV_data_management_handbook.pdf

Agisoft Metashape, 2022, User Manual: Professional Edition, Version 1.8